

PREPARATION AND PROPERTIES OF SELF-HEALING CARBON FIBER REINFORCED EPOXY COMPOSITE

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1 Introduction

Inside cracks in structural composites is hard to be detected and repaired. Therefore, active polymeric materials incorporating self-healing functionality have attracted more and more attention because they represent a new paradigm for structural materials that require long-term durability and reliability. [1-8] Many of works have focused on binary self-healing system such as endo-dicyclopentadiene and its catalysts[1, 9-13], epoxy and its curing agents[5, 6, 14]. In this paper, self-healing carbon fiber reinforced epoxy composite was prepared using binary healing system consisting of epoxy-containing microcapsules and imidazoline derivatives curing agent based on anionic polymerization. When crack propagates along the interface of carbon fiber and matrix in the composite, the embedded microcapsule is ruptured and the epoxy healing agent flows out as result of capillary action. Finally, polymerization of healing agent occurs to bond cracks due to the contact with embedded hardener. The imidazoline derivatives curing agent used in this study is latent curing agent which can be well dispersed in epoxy matrix during composite manufacturing. The microcapsules used in binary healing system are prepared by situ polymerization of urea and formaldehyde in an oil-in-water emulsion. The microcapsules possess rough surface morphology, less adhesion, less core material permeability, appropriate diameter and core content, and adequate stability. In this paper, the protocol of interlaminar healing efficiency of composite was proposed and self-healing performance was evaluated. In our former work, it was found that the distribution of microcapsules and latent curing agent greatly influences the healing efficiency but not the stoichiometric composition, and the optimal weight ratio of microcapsules and

curing agent was concluded. SEM photographs of fractured surface of self-healing composite of virgin and healed specimen are observed to provide an intuitional judgment for the self-healing process. The recovery of tensile strength carbon fiber reinforced epoxy composite were investigated so as to provide parameters for making self-healing composite products.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

Epoxy resin (diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A: DGEBA, E-51) used as core material and matrix of composite was purchased from Wuxi Resin Plant, China. Epoxy-containing microcapsules were synthesized via situ-polymerization of urea and formaldehyde in an oil-in-water emulsion. 2,4-diamino-6-[2'-methyl imidazolyl-(1)']-ethyl-triazine (2MZ-AZINE) used as anionic hardener was obtained from Shikoku Chemical Corporation, Japan. Triethylenetetramine (TETA) used as curing agent of matrix was purchased from Tianjin Yixin Tenglong Chemical Plant, China. All the materials are commercial products and were used without further purification.

2.2 Preparation of self-healing carbon fiber reinforced epoxy composite

The resin mixture was prepared by mixing 100 parts E-51 epoxide with 13 parts TETA curing agent. Then, the microcapsules and 2MZ-AZINE curing agent were added to the resin mixture under ultrasonic agitation. Then the mixture was degassed in a vacuum oven. The self-healing composite was fabricated by winding process on the flat plate mold. Solvent is not used in the work of fabricating composite. Resultant composite was degassed in a

vacuum oven for 30min. Eventually, composite was cured for 48h at room temperature, followed by postcuring at 80°C for 1h.

2.3 Characterization

Fractured surface of self-healing carbon fiber reinforced epoxy composite was observed by SEM (QUANTA 200 ESEM, FEI). Samples were prepared on an aluminium slice, dried in a vacuum oven, and sputtered a coat with gold-palladium.

To evaluate recovery of interlaminar properties of composites containing microcapsules and hardener, Five samples were tested. In our former work, the optimal weight ratio of microcapsules and curing agent 2MZ-AZINE are 15 wt% and 2 wt% for epoxy resin, offering a ~83% healing efficiency.[15] The healing Efficiency is defined as the ratio of tensile stress, K_{IC} , of healed and virgin materials. The epoxy composite were measured according to the Chinese standard GB/T 1447-1983. A tester (INSTRON 5569) was used at a crosshead speed of 2 mm/min. Five samples (180 mm in length, 5 mm in thickness and 10 mm in width) were tested for each case. The original specimens were tested to failure, giving the tensile stress, K_{IC}^0 . Load was then removed, allowing the crack faces to come back into contact and to be self-healed in an oven preset at 120°C for 2h. The healed specimens were tested again and yielded the tensile stress, K_{IC}^1 . Accordingly, the crack healing efficiency η can be calculated by (1)

$$\eta = \frac{K_{IC}^0}{K_{IC}^1} \tag{1}$$

3 Results and Discussion

Self-healing process

Table 1 Interlaminar tensile stress and self-healing properties of carbon fiber reinforced epoxy composite

Sample No.	virgin(MPa)	healed(MPa)	Healing efficiency (%)
1	24.04127	4.31812	18.0
2	23.76047	2.60031	11.0

3	24.40873	7.06431	28.9
4	21.79413	10.00964	45.9
5	20.49706	11.50804	56.1
average			31.98

The average self-healing efficiency in this research is 31.98% recovery of interlaminar tensile stress. Table 1 shows the interlaminar tensile stress and self-healing properties of carbon fiber reinforced epoxy composite. Figure 1 shows SEM photographs of fractured surface of self-healing composite. From Fig. 1 (a), the rough microcapsule’s shell inlaid into matrix can be obviously observed, which is caused by the release of healing agent and leaving an empty microcapsule’s shell. Additionally, the interface join between microcapsules and matrix is strong due to the mechanical engagement of microcapsule’s shell that possesses rough outside. As is shown in Fig. 1 (b), compared with virgin specimen, the fractured surface of healed specimen is smooth and covered with polymer film, which infers that self-healing process is successfully achieved.

Fig.1. SEM photographs of fractured surface of self-healing composite. (a) Virgin and (b) healed specimen.

4 Conclusions

In this paper, preparation process of self-healing carbon fiber reinforced epoxy composite is introduced. Self-healing efficiency Self-healing process of epoxy composite with carbon fiber reinforced is demonstrated by SEM photographs of fractured surface of self-healing composite. In our full paper, the protocol of self-healing efficiency of composite was proposed and self-healing performance was evaluated. The tensile strength and flexural strength of self-healing carbon fiber reinforced epoxy composite were investigated so as to provide parameters for making self-healing composite products.

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